

International Journal of Basic, Applied, and Innovative Research

IJBAIR, 2026, 14(1): 12-29

ISSN: 2315 - 5388

www.arpijournals.com; www.antrescentpub.com.

E-ISSN: 2384 - 681X

RESEARCH PAPER

DETERMINANTS OF ALCOHOL AND OTHER PSYCHOACTIVE SUBSTANCE USE AMONG UNDERGRADUATES IN A NIGERIAN UNIVERSITY: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

AZEKE Olohita Diane¹ and AZEKE Akhator Terence*²¹Department of Family Medicine, Faculty of Clinical Sciences, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma. Nigeria;²Department of Anatomic Pathology Irrua Specialist Teaching Hospital, Nigeria.Correspondence: akhator2001@yahoo.com

Received: 2nd January , 2026

Accepted: 29th January, 2026Published: 31st January , 2026*Endorsed By: Innovative Science Research Foundation (ISREF) and International Society of Science Researchers (ISSCIR).**Indexed By: African Journal Online (AJOL) and IRMS Informatics India (J-Gate)*

ABSTRACT

This study examined socio-demographic and psychosocial determinants of alcohol and other psychoactive substance use among undergraduates of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma. A cross-sectional analytical study was conducted from January to March 2025 among 319 full-time undergraduates selected through multistage sampling. Data were collected using a pre-tested, adapted ESPAD-based questionnaire. Current substance use was defined as use of any psychoactive substance within the preceding 30 days. Bivariate associations were assessed using chi-square tests, and variables with $p < 0.20$ were entered into multivariable logistic regression. Adjusted odds ratios (AORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were reported. The mean age of participants was 21.3 ± 2.9 years, and 53.3% were male. Alcohol was most prevalent (59.6%), followed by tobacco (20.4%), cannabis (14.7%), opioids (9.4%), cocaine (6.3%), hallucinogens (4.7%), and inhalants (0.9%). Substance use was significantly ($p = 0.01$) higher among males than females. In multivariable analysis, male sex independently predicted use (AOR = 2.10; 95% CI: 1.28–3.44). Psychosocial motivations demonstrated strong independent associations: curiosity (AOR = 19.3; 95% CI: 4.6–30.8), pleasure-seeking (AOR = 9.9; 95% CI: 4.5–21.8), sociability (AOR = 10.4; 95% CI: 2.4–15.4), mood stimulation (AOR = 9.0; 95% CI: 2.1–28.1), relief from psychological distress (AOR = 8.2; 95% CI: 2.9–23.1), and staying awake (AOR = 6.8; 95% CI: 2.3–10.1). Substance use is common among undergraduates and is more strongly associated with psychosocial motivations than demographic characteristics. Targeted, context-specific prevention strategies are warranted.

Keywords: Substance-Related Disorders; Alcohol Drinking; Cannabis; University Students; Nigeria; Psychosocial Factors

INTRODUCTION

Psychoactive substances, both licit and illicit, are chemical agents that alter mood, perception, cognition, and behaviour when ingested or administered (Schifano *et al.*, 2021). Their use constitutes a major global public health concern (Armoon *et al.*, 2023). According to the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC, 2023), approximately 296 million people worldwide used drugs at least once in the past year, while about 39.5 million people were living with drug use disorders. These figures distinguish between general use and problematic use, clarifying that drug use

disorders represent a subset of total users. Young people aged 15–34 years account for a substantial proportion of users globally, making university and tertiary populations particularly vulnerable.

Nigeria, with its large youth population, has seen a sharp rise in the use of substances such as alcohol, tobacco, cannabis, benzodiazepines, cocaine, and opioids (Elemile *et al.*, 2023). The 2018 National Drug Use Survey estimated that 14.4% of Nigerians aged 15–64 years had used drugs (excluding alcohol and tobacco) in the past year, a prevalence higher than the global average reported at the time (Jatau *et al.*, 2021). Among university students, prevalence rates are considerably higher. Regional evidence indicates striking variability, with the South-South zone, particularly Benin City, recording some of the highest prevalence rates (Bio-sya *et al.*, 2022). Studies report lifetime use of psychoactive substances among Nigerian undergraduates ranging between 30.5% and 65% (Okoro and Chikezie, 2024; Olorunfemi *et al.*, 2024), while current use (past 30 days or past year) varies across institutions and regions. This far exceeding rates in the general population, with alcohol consistently emerging as the most commonly used substance across all regions (Dumbili, 2024).

Beyond alcohol, other substances such as tobacco, cannabis, stimulants, and sedatives also show varying prevalence across the country. Tobacco use has been reported as high as 81% in South-West Nigeria, while sedative use ranges between 6.1% and 7.3%, and cannabis between 1.4% and 20% (Lasebikan *et al.*, 2019; Oyewole *et al.*, 2018; Umana *et al.*, 2014). Gender disparities have been documented, with male students generally reporting higher use of alcohol, tobacco, and cannabis, although some studies in the South-South region observed higher current use among females (Johnson *et al.*, 2017; Ogunkunle *et al.*, 2020). Similar patterns have been reported in other African countries such as Ghana, Kenya and Ethiopia, where curiosity, peer influence, and emotional distress were major drivers of substance use (Kyei-Gyamfi *et al.*, 2024; Musyoka *et al.*, 2020; Mutiso *et al.*, 2022; Necho *et al.*, 2020). These trends highlight an urgent need to understand the socio-demographic and psychosocial determinants of substance use among Nigerian undergraduates, as such insights are vital for developing culturally relevant, evidence-based prevention and intervention strategies.

Despite growing awareness of the risks associated with psychoactive substance use, limited empirical evidence exists on the underlying determinants influencing these behaviours among undergraduates in semi-urban Nigerian settings such as Ekpoma. The university environment, often characterised by academic stress, peer influence, social experimentation, and limited access to counselling services, may predispose students to substance initiation and continued use. Understanding these contextual and psychosocial factors is essential for designing effective prevention and intervention strategies tailored to the needs of young people in higher institutions. Therefore, this study aims to examine the determinants influencing the use of alcohol and other psychoactive substances among undergraduates of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design and Setting: A cross-sectional analytical approach was adopted for this investigation because it is well suited to determining prevalence rates and assessing relationships between exposure variables (socio-demographic and psychosocial characteristics) and outcome variables (substance use behaviours) within a defined population at a single point in time. The study was conducted among undergraduate students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, from January to March 2025. The three-month data collection window coincided with an active academic semester, ensuring adequate student availability across faculties and levels of study, thereby improving representativeness and reducing the potential influence of seasonal or vacation-related variations in student attendance. Ekpoma is situated approximately 87 kilometres from Benin City, a major commercial centre in the South-South region of Nigeria. At the time of the study, the university comprised twelve faculties with an undergraduate population exceeding 25,000 students.

Theoretical Framework: Guided by Social Learning Theory and the Theory of Planned Behavior as depicted in Figure 1, this study adopts an integrated conceptual framework that explains psychoactive substance use as a product of social

modelling, peer reinforcement, and cognitive determinants. While Social Learning Theory emphasises the role of observational learning and peer influence within the university environment, the Theory of Planned Behavior posits that attitudes toward substance use, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control shape behavioural intention, which subsequently predicts actual behaviour (Bandura and Walters, 1977; Ajzen, 1991). Within this framework, it is hypothesised that socio-demographic and psychosocial factors will significantly predict behavioural intention and, in turn, the use of alcohol and other psychoactive substances among undergraduates of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Research and Ethics Committee of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma (Approval No: AAU/REC/PH/2024/023). Permission was also secured from faculty deans and departmental heads before data collection. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained in writing from each respondent. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout, with no personal identifiers recorded. The study adhered to the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki (2013 revision).

Figure 1: Social Learning Theory and Theory of Planned Behavior

Eligibility Criteria: Participants were eligible if they were officially registered full-time undergraduate students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, aged 16 years and above, present on campus during the study period, and willing to provide informed consent (or assent in accordance with ethical approval for those below 18 years). Inclusion of students aged 16 years and above ensured representation of all admitted undergraduates, as university entry in Nigeria occurs at age. Excluded from participating in the study were students enrolled in part-time, distance-learning, or sandwich programmes were excluded to maintain homogeneity in exposure to the on-campus academic and social environment. Additionally, postgraduate students and individuals who declined consent or provided incomplete questionnaires were excluded from the final analysis.

Sample Size Determination and Sampling Technique: The sample size was determined using the Cochran formula for cross-sectional studies (Sugden *et al.*, 2000):

$$N = Z^2 p(1-p)/d^2$$

where $Z = 1.96$ (95% confidence level), $p = 0.5$ (assumed prevalence of substance use due to lack of precise institutional data), and $d = 0.05$ (margin of error).

The calculated minimum sample size was 384. After adjusting for an anticipated 10% non-response rate, 422 students were approached. A total of 319 fully completed questionnaires were returned (a response rate of 75.6%).

Although the final sample was below the calculated minimum, a post-hoc power analysis using G*Power 3.1 for a two-tailed test at $\alpha = 0.05$, assuming a moderate effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.3$), indicated a statistical power of 81%, exceeding the conventional 80% threshold. Comparison of respondents' demographics with institutional records showed no substantial differences in age, gender, or faculty distribution, suggesting minimal non-response bias. Therefore, analysis proceeded with $n = 319$, with the reduced sample size acknowledged as a limitation affecting precision and generalisability of subgroup estimates.

A multistage sampling approach was employed. In the first stage, four faculties were randomly selected using simple random sampling (balloting without replacement). In the second stage, two departments were selected from each chosen faculty through random selection. Finally, proportionate stratified sampling was used to determine the number of participants per department and year of study, after which systematic random sampling was applied to select individual respondents from departmental registers.

Data Collection Instrument: Data were collected using a pre-tested, semi-structured, self-administered questionnaire adapted from the European School Survey Project on Alcohol and Other Drugs (ESPAD) (Mokinaro *et al.*, 2020). Although ESPAD was originally designed for adolescents aged 15–16 years (REF), the instrument was systematically adapted for undergraduate students through item selection (retaining relevant alcohol, tobacco, cannabis, stimulant, and sedative items), contextual modification (rewording questions to reflect age-appropriate language and university experiences), addition of items on academic stress and other psycho-social determinants, and expert review by three public health specialists to ensure content validity and cultural relevance. The questionnaire comprised four sections: socio-demographics, substance use patterns, substance use behaviour, and psycho-social drivers of substance use. Construct validity was assessed via exploratory factor analysis (EFA), which confirmed factorability (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin = 0.82; Bartlett's test $\chi^2 = 1050.3$, $p < 0.001$). Principal component analysis with varimax rotation extracted two factors—substance use behaviour and psycho-social drivers of substance use—explaining 63.5% of the total variance, with all items loading ≥ 0.45 on their respective factors. Internal consistency for the dichotomous substance use items was confirmed using Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20 = 0.84), with α values ranging from 0.74 to 0.81 across the two factors. Pretesting and psychometric evaluation confirmed that the adapted instrument reliably and validly captured alcohol and psychoactive substance use patterns and their psychosocial determinants among undergraduate students.

Study Variables: The primary outcome of this study was current substance use, defined as self-reported use of any psychoactive substance (alcohol, tobacco, cannabis, stimulants, or sedatives) within the 30 days preceding the survey, dichotomised as Yes (1) for users and No (0) for non-users. Independent variables included socio-demographic characteristics (age, sex, level of study, faculty, and living arrangement) and psychosocial factors (curiosity, pleasure-seeking, relief from psychological distress, mood stimulation, sociability, staying awake, and academic performance enhancement), all measured as binary-response items (Yes = 1, No = 0) and asked of all students to allow comparison between users and non-users. Variables with p -values < 0.20 in bivariate analyses were entered into multivariable logistic regression to identify independent determinants of current substance use.

Data Collection Procedure: Trained research assistants, comprising postgraduate students in public health, administered the questionnaires during lecture-free periods to minimize classroom disruption. The study objectives were explained, confidentiality assured, and informed consent obtained. Completed questionnaires were collected immediately to reduce data loss. Respondents were instructed not to provide identifying information to maintain anonymity and enhance truthful reporting.

Data Management and Statistical Analysis: Data were cleaned, coded, and entered into EpiData Manager before being exported to IBM SPSS Statistics version 26 for analysis. Descriptive statistics were computed to summarize the socio-demographic characteristics and the prevalence of psychoactive substance use. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables were summarized using means and standard deviations, as appropriate. Bivariate analyses were conducted using Pearson's Chi-square (χ^2) test or Fisher's Exact test where assumptions for the Chi-square test were not met to examine associations between independent variables (socio-demographic and psycho-social factors) and current substance use (yes/no). Variables with p-values <0.20 at the bivariate level were entered into a multivariable binary logistic regression model to identify independent determinants. Adjusted odds ratios (AORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were reported to estimate the strength of associations while controlling for potential confounders. Model fit was evaluated using the Hosmer-Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test, and multicollinearity was assessed using variance inflation factors (VIFs), with values >5 indicating potential collinearity. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered indicative of statistical significance.

Data Availability and Ethical Compliance: The datasets generated and analysed during this study are not publicly available due to the sensitive nature of the information and the need to protect participant confidentiality but are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request and with permission from the Research and Ethics Committee of Ambrose Alli University. All data were anonymised prior to analysis, and no personally identifiable information was collected. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before enrolment; for respondents aged 16–17 years, assent was obtained in accordance with the approved minimal-risk protocol. Signed consent and assent forms were securely stored in a locked cabinet accessible only to the principal investigator, while electronic data were password-protected and stored on an encrypted computer.

RESULTS

Socio-demographic Characteristics of Participants

Table 1 summarizes the socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants. The majority of respondents (66.5%) were aged 20–24 years, and a slightly higher proportion were male (53.3%). Most participants identified as Christians (93.4%), reflecting the predominant religious affiliation within the study population. In terms of academic standing, the largest proportion of students (34.8%) was in their 400 level of study. Nearly all respondents were single (97.8%) and the majority (87.8%) originated from monogamous family settings. With respect to accommodation, 80.6% of students resided on campus, while over half (62.7%) reported receiving a monthly allowance of less than ₦60,000.

Pattern of Substance Use among Undergraduate Students

As presented in Figure 2, alcohol was the most commonly used substance, reported by 59.6% of respondents, while 40.4% had never used it. Tobacco use was reported by 20.4%, and cannabis by 14.7% of participants. Opioid use accounted for 9.4%, whereas 6.3% had used cocaine. Hallucinogen use was reported by 4.7% and inhalant use by 0.9% of respondents.

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Participants

Variables	Frequency (n=319)	Percentages (%)
Age group		
15 – 19	77	24.1
20 -24	212	66.5
25 – 29	29	9.1
≥ 30	1	0.3
Mean Age (years)	21.31 ± 2.93	
Sex		
Male	170	53.3
Female	149	46.7
Religion		
Christianity	298	93.4
Islam	19	6.0
Traditional	2	0.6
Year of study		
100L	28	8.8
200L	71	22.3
300L	86	27.0
400L	111	34.8
500L	20	6.3
600L	3	0.9
Marital status		
Single	312	97.8
Married	5	1.6
Divorced	2	0.6
Family type		
Monogamous	280	87.8
Polygamous	36	11.3
Extended	3	0.9
Type of residence		
On Campus	257	80.6
Off Campus	62	19.4
Monthly allowance (₦)		
<60,000	200	62.7
> 60,000 – 100,000	92	28.8
> 100,000	27	8.5

Figure 2: Pattern of Substance Use among Undergraduate Students

Alcohol: beer, wine, spirits, palm wine, ogogoro; Tobacco: cigarette, chewing tobacco, cigar, cola; Cannabis: marijuana, wee-wee, igbo, pot, hashish, monkey-tail; Opioids: heroin, morphine, codeine; Cocaine: coke, crack, gbana; Hallucinogens (LSD, PCP; Inhalants: nitrous oxide, glue, petrol

Socio-demographic Determinants of Substance Use

Table 2 presents the relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and substance use among respondents. Although the prevalence of substance use increased with age, this association was not statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 1.267, p = 0.05$). A significant association was observed between sex and substance use ($\chi^2 = 9.580, p = 0.01$), with a markedly higher prevalence among males (74.1%) compared to females (57.7%). Substance use varied by year of study, peaking among 400-level students (69.4%), though the variation was not significant ($\chi^2 = 6.795, p = 0.22$). Similarly, marital status, religion, family structure, type of residence, and monthly allowance showed no significant associations with substance use. Nonetheless, higher proportions were observed among single (66.7%), Christian (66.8%), and polygamous-family (80.6%) students, as well as those living off-campus (71.0%) and receiving higher monthly allowances (77.8%).

Socio-Demographic Predictors of Current Substance Use

In the multivariable model adjusting for all socio-demographic characteristics (Table 3), male sex emerged as the only clear independent predictor of current substance use, with males demonstrating significantly higher odds compared with females. Students from polygamous family settings also showed increased odds of current substance use, with the association reaching borderline statistical significance. Age group, year of study, marital status, religion, type of residence, and monthly allowance were not independently associated with current substance use after adjustment. Although higher academic level and greater monthly allowance showed trends toward increased odds, these associations did not achieve statistical significance.

Psycho-Social Drivers of Substance Use among Undergraduate Students

Table 4 presents the association between the psycho-social drivers of substance use and actual substance use behaviour among the respondents. Among the factors examined, academic performance was the only variable not significantly associated with substance use ($\chi^2 = 2.437, p = 0.064$). In contrast, several psycho-social motivations demonstrated

Table 2: Socio-demographic determinants of substance use among undergraduate students

Socio-demographic Characteristics	Current Substance use		χ^2 /Fishers Exact	p-value
	Yes	No		
Age group				
15 – 19	48 (62.3)	29 (37.7)	1.267	0.05*
20 – 24	143 (67.5)	69 (32.5)		
25 – 29	20 (69.0)	9 (31.0)		
≥30	0 (0.0)	1 (100.0)		
Sex				
Male	126 (74.1)	44 (25.9)	9.580	0.01**
Female	86 (57.7)	63 (42.3)		
Year of study				
100L	16 (57.1)	12 (42.9)	6.795	0.22
200L	48 (67.6)	23 (32.4)		
300L	58 (67.4)	28 (32.6)		
400L	77 (69.4)	34 (30.6)		
500L	13 (65.0)	7 (35.0)		
600L	0 (0.0)	3 (100.0)		
Marital status				
Single	208 (66.7)	104 (33.3)	0.858	1.00
Married	3 (60.0)	2 (40.0)		
Divorced	1 (50.0)	1 (50.0)		
Religion				
Christianity	199 (66.8)	99 (33.2)	1.333	0.52
Islam	11 (57.9)	8 (42.1)		
Traditional	2 (66.7)	0 (0.0)		
Family setting				
Monogamous	181 (64.8)	99 (35.4)	3.818	0.12
Polygamous	29 (80.6)	7 (19.4)		
Type of residence				
On campus	168 (65.4)	89 (34.6)	0.702	0.40
Off campus	44 (71.0)	18 (29.0)		
Monthly allowance				
< 60,000	129 (64.5)	71 (35.5)	1.932	0.37
>60,000 – 100,000	62 (67.4)	30 (32.6)		
>100,000	21 (77.8)	6 (22.2)		

χ^2 – chi-square; *statistically significant at p-less than 0.05; **statistically significant at p-less than 0.01

statistically significant associations ($p < 0.05$). A markedly higher proportion of participants who identified curiosity as a reason for substance use (96.6%) reported engaging in substance use ($\chi^2 = 29.524$, $p = 0.001$). Similarly, substance use was more prevalent among respondents who cited pleasure ($\chi^2 = 44.425$, $p = 0.001$), relief from psychological

distress ($\chi^2 = 20.574$, $p = 0.001$), mood stimulation ($\chi^2 = 12.471$, $p = 0.001$), sociability ($\chi^2 = 14.865$, $p = 0.001$), and staying awake ($\chi^2 = 16.108$, $p = 0.001$)

Table 3: Multivariable Logistic Regression of Socio-Demographic Determinants of Current Substance Use among Undergraduate Students

Variable	Category	B (Coefficient)	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p-value
Age group	15–19	Reference	1	–
	20–29	0.22	1.25 (0.72–2.18)	0.43
	≥30	–	–	Excluded due to n=1
Sex	Female	Reference	1	–
	Male	0.74	2.10 (1.28–3.44)	0.01*
Year of study	100–200L	Reference	1	–
	300–400L	0.46	1.59 (0.91–2.78)	0.10
	500–600L	0.42	1.52 (0.50–4.63)	0.46
Marital status	Single	Reference	1	–
	Married/Divorced	-0.15	0.86 (0.26–2.85)	0.81
Religion	Christianity	Reference	1	–
	Non-Christian	-0.24	0.79 (0.36–1.74)	0.55
Family setting	Monogamous	Reference	1	–
	Polygamous	0.82	2.26 (1.00–5.08)	0.05*
Type of residence	On campus	Reference	1	–
	Off campus	0.27	1.31 (0.70–2.44)	0.40
Monthly allowance	<60,000	Reference	1	–
	60,001–100,000	0.12	1.13 (0.66–1.94)	0.66
	>100,000	0.65	1.92 (0.80–4.61)	0.14

Independent Psychosocial Predictors of Current Substance Use

After simultaneous adjustment for all psychosocial variables (Table 5), several motivational factors remained independently associated with current substance use. Curiosity demonstrated the strongest association with current use, followed by pleasure-seeking, enhanced sociability, mood stimulation, relief from psychological distress, and the need to stay awake. In contrast, use motivated by academic performance enhancement was not statistically significant in the adjusted model.

Table 4: Other Determinants of Substance Use among Undergraduate Students

Factors	Current Substance use		χ^2 /Fishers Exact	p-value
	Yes	No		
Curiosity to engage in substance use				
No	155 (59.6)	105 (40.4)	29.52	0.01**
Yes	57 (96.6)	2 (3.4)		
Substance Use for Pleasure				
No	118 (54.4)	99 (45.6)	44.43	0.01**
Yes	94 (92.2)	8 (7.8)		
Relief from Psychological distress				
No	161 (61.0)	103 (39.0)	20.57	0.01**
Yes	51 (92.7)	4 (7.3)		
Substance Use for Mood stimulation				
No	181 (63.3)	105 (36.70)	12.47	0.01**
Yes	31 (93.9)	2 (6.1)		
Substance use for sociability				
No	177 (62.8)	105 (37.2)	14.87	0.01**
Yes	35 (94.6)	2 (5.4)		
Substance Use To keep awake				
No	168 (62.0)	103 (38.0)	16.11	
Yes	44 (91.7)	4 (6.3)		
Substance use for Academic performance				
No	197 (65.4)	104 (34.6)	2.44	0.06
Yes	15 (83.3)	3 (16.7)		

χ^2 – chi-square; *statistically significant at p-less than 0.05; **statistically significant at p-less than 0.01

Table 5: Multivariable Logistic Regression of Psychosocial Determinants of Current Substance Use

Variable	Category	B (Coefficient)	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p-value
Curiosity	No	Reference	1	–
	Yes	2.96	19.3 (4.6–30.8)	<0.001*
Pleasure	No	Reference	1	–
	Yes	2.29	9.9 (4.5–21.8)	<0.001*
Relief from psychological distress	No	Reference	1	–
	Yes	2.10	8.2 (2.9–23.1)	<0.001*
Mood stimulation	No	Reference	1	–
	Yes	2.20	9.0 (2.1–28.1)	<0.001*
Sociability	No	Reference	1	–
	Yes	2.34	10.4 (2.4–15.4)	<0.001*
Keep awake	No	Reference	1	–
	Yes	1.91	6.8 (2.3–10.1)	<0.001*
Academic performance	No	Reference	1	–
	Yes	0.97	2.6 (0.7–9.6)	0.15

*statistically significant at *p*-less than 0.01

DISCUSSION

This study examined psychoactive substance use and its associated factors among undergraduate students of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma. The findings indicate a high prevalence of substance use within this population, with alcohol emerging as the most commonly used substance (59.6%). This pattern is consistent with prior reports from Nigerian universities, where alcohol remains the predominant psychoactive substance among students (Adesida *et al.*, 2022; Wada *et al.*, 2021). Comparable prevalence levels have been documented in Benin City (46.6%), Ibadan (31.3%), and Jos (44.4%) (Adeyemo-Florence *et al.*, 2016; Asagba *et al.*, 2021; Okafor *et al.*, 2022). Although direct comparisons should be interpreted cautiously due to methodological differences, the convergence of findings across institutions suggests that alcohol consumption is a persistent feature of student social environments in Nigeria.

At the regional and global levels, this pattern aligns with epidemiological evidence reported by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. According to the World Drug Report 2023, an estimated 2.3 billion people worldwide are current alcohol users, making alcohol prevalence of 59% for this age group the most widely consumed psychoactive substance globally (UNODC, 2024; Danpanichkul *et al.*, 2025). The report further indicates that substance use prevalence is highest among young adults aged 18–25 years, with this age group demonstrating disproportionately elevated levels of experimentation and regular consumption compared to older cohorts. These figures reinforce the observed trend in the present study, where alcohol use predominated among participants within the 20–24-year age bracket, reflecting the broader demographic vulnerability consistently documented in international surveillance data (Li *et al.*, 2025). The consistency between the present findings and broader UNODC estimates strengthens the external validity of the results and indicates that alcohol use among undergraduates in this setting reflects broader youth consumption patterns rather than an isolated institutional phenomenon.

Other substances were reported less frequently, including tobacco (20.4%), cannabis (14.7%), opioids (9.4%), cocaine (6.3%), hallucinogens (4.7%), and inhalants (0.9%). These rates are broadly consistent with Nigerian studies reporting

similar hierarchies of substance preference (Airede and Asibor, 2025; Owolabi *et al.*, 2021). Cannabis remains the most commonly reported illicit substance, in line with UNODC regional data indicating cannabis as the most prevalent illicit drug in West Africa (WHO, 2024). The relatively lower prevalence of cocaine and hallucinogens may reflect higher cost, limited availability, and enforcement patterns, as reported by Scheibe *et al.* (2024) who noted that the distribution and consumption of cocaine and hallucinogenic substances in many sub-Saharan African settings remain constrained by higher market prices, supply chain limitations, and intensified drug control measures compared with more widely available substances such as alcohol and cannabis. Similarly, Emmanuel *et al.* (2024) observed that in university populations, stimulant and hallucinogen use was comparatively low and often restricted to specific social subgroups, largely due to cost barriers and limited access networks. These structural and market dynamics may partly explain the lower prevalence observed in the present study.

With respect to socio-demographic characteristics, male sex emerged as the only clear independent factor associated with current substance use after adjustment. Male students demonstrated more than twice the odds of substance use compared with females (AOR = 2.10; 95% CI: 1.28–3.44; $p = 0.01$). The magnitude of this association indicates a moderate but meaningful difference between sexes. This finding is consistent with studies across Nigeria and sub-Saharan Africa demonstrating higher prevalence of alcohol and drug use among male students (Alebachew *et al.*, 2019; Oluoha *et al.*, 2017; Htet *et al.*, 2020). While sociocultural norms that tolerate male risk-taking behaviours have been proposed as explanatory frameworks (Merdassa, 2024), the cross-sectional design of this study does not allow causal inference. Nonetheless, the persistence of the association in multivariable analysis suggests that sex remains an important correlate of substance use within this context. This was corroborated by Ekekezie *et al.* (2024), who demonstrated that male university students in a Nigeria had significantly higher odds of current alcohol and other substance use compared with their female counterparts, even after adjusting for socio-demographic and psychosocial factors.

Family setting also demonstrated a borderline statistically significant association. Students from polygamous families had over twice the odds of current substance use compared with those from monogamous families (AOR = 2.26; 95% CI: 1.00–5.08; $p = 0.05$). Although the confidence interval indicates some imprecision, likely due to smaller subgroup size, the magnitude of association suggests a potentially meaningful relationship. Similar associations have been reported in some Nigerian studies where variations in family structure were linked to behavioural outcomes among adolescents and young adults (Onwudebe and Elechi, 2025; Uwaibi *et al.*, 2022). Other socio-demographic variables, including age group, year of study, marital status, religion, type of residence, and monthly allowance, were not independently associated with substance use after adjustment. The attenuation of these effects after adjustment suggests that structural demographic characteristics may exert less influence than proximal psychosocial motivations in explaining substance use behaviour in this cohort. This supports the findings of Espinosa *et al.* (2023), who reported that psychological distress and coping-related motives were stronger predictors of substance use than socio-demographic variables among university students, and Tunagur and Kurt Tunagur (2026), who observed that behavioural and psychosocial factors consistently outweighed demographic characteristics in multivariate models of student substance use across several low- and middle-income countries.

Psychosocial factors demonstrated substantially stronger associations with current substance use than socio-demographic characteristics. Curiosity emerged as the most pronounced associated factor, with students reporting curiosity having nearly twenty times the odds of substance use (AOR = 19.3; 95% CI: 4.6–30.8; $p < 0.001$). This large effect size indicates a robust association, even after controlling for other psychosocial variables. Similar findings have been reported in Ghana and South Africa, where curiosity and experimentation are common entry pathways into substance use among university students (Attila *et al.*, 2023; Govender *et al.*, 2017). While the directionality of this relationship cannot be established in a cross-sectional design, the strength of association suggests that experimentation motives play a central role in student substance use patterns. This assertion was supported by Willoughby *et al.* (2021), who reported that risk-taking and novelty-seeking behaviours peak during emerging adulthood, making experimentation with psychoactive substances a developmentally normative, yet high-risk, exploratory behaviour in university

populations. Likewise, Melendro *et al.* (2020) observed that the transition into young adulthood is characterised by increased autonomy and exposure to peer contexts that facilitate substance experimentation, thereby reinforcing curiosity-driven initiation

Pleasure-seeking (AOR = 9.9; 95% CI: 4.5–21.8), sociability (AOR = 10.4; 95% CI: 2.4–15.4), mood stimulation (AOR = 9.0; 95% CI: 2.1–28.1), and relief from psychological distress (AOR = 8.2; 95% CI: 2.9–23.1) were also strongly associated with substance use. These effect sizes, ranging from approximately eight- to ten-fold increased odds, indicate substantial associations between internal motivational states and behavioural outcomes. Compared with the two-fold association observed for male sex, psychosocial motivations appear to exert considerably stronger associations with substance use in this population. These findings are consistent with prior research indicating that hedonic and coping motives frequently underlie student substance use (Caricati and Ferrari, 2021; Xin *et al.*, 2025). However, it cannot be determined whether psychological distress preceded substance use or resulted from it. The association between substance use and the need to stay awake (AOR = 6.8; 95% CI: 2.3–10.1; $p < 0.001$) suggests that academic demands may indirectly shape consumption patterns. Similar findings have been reported in studies examining stimulant and alcohol use during examination periods (Mousavi *et al.*, 2024; Palin and McConville, 2021). Notably, substance use motivated by academic performance enhancement did not remain statistically significant in the adjusted model (AOR = 2.6; 95% CI: 0.7–9.6; $p = 0.15$). This suggests that perceived cognitive enhancement may be less influential when other motivations are simultaneously considered.

However, this study has several limitations. The cross-sectional design precludes causal or temporal inferences, making it unclear whether psychosocial motivations preceded substance use or were retrospectively endorsed by current users. The use of self-administered, self-reported measures may have introduced recall and social desirability biases, potentially resulting in underestimation of prevalence. The smaller-than-planned sample size and sparse cell counts in some categories may have reduced statistical power and contributed to wide confidence intervals, limiting the precision of certain estimates. Furthermore, restriction to students from five faculties raises the possibility of selection bias and may limit generalisability to the broader university population, given potential differences in academic culture and peer environments across faculties. Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable evidence-based insights into both structural and psychosocial correlates of substance use among undergraduates. By simultaneously examining socio-demographic and motivational associated factors, it contributes nuanced understanding to an area that remains underexplored in comparable university settings. Future multi-institutional studies with larger, more diverse samples and longitudinal designs would strengthen the evidence base and enhance external validity.

Conclusion

Psychoactive substance use is a notable concern among undergraduates at Ambrose Alli University, with alcohol, tobacco, and cannabis predominating. Male students were more than twice as likely to report current substance use compared with females, and psychosocial motivations emerged as the most robust correlates: curiosity, pleasure-seeking, enhanced sociability, mood stimulation, relief from psychological distress, and the need to stay awake were all independently associated with use. In contrast, structural demographic characteristics such as age, year of study, residence, and financial allowance showed limited independent associations. These findings suggest that proximal psychosocial motivations are more strongly associated with substance use patterns than conventional demographic characteristics in this setting. These results may inform the development of university-based prevention approaches targeting motivational and social-contextual factors. Longitudinal and multi-centre studies are warranted to clarify temporal relationships and assess intervention effectiveness. Conflict of interests

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests.

Funding

The authors received no financial support for the research, authorship, or publication of this article.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION

Conceptualization: Azeke AT; Data curation: Azeke OD; Formal analysis: Azeke OD; Funding acquisition: Azeke AT and Azeke OD; Investigation: Azeke AT F and Azeke OD; Methodology: Azeke AT and Azeke OD; Project administration: Azeke OD; Supervision: Azeke AT; Validation: Azeke AT; Original Draft Writing: Azeke AT; Writing–Review and Editing: Azeke AT and Azeke OD

REFERENCES

Aboagye, R. G., Kugbey, N., Ahinkorah, B. O., Seidu, A.-A., Cadri, A. and Akonor, P. Y. (2021). Alcohol consumption among tertiary students in the Hohoe municipality, Ghana: analysis of prevalence, effects, and associated factors from a cross-sectional study. *BMC Psychiatry*; 21(1): 431. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-021-03447-0>

Adesida, S. A., Quadri, M. O. and Adedeji, A. M. (2022). Use of psychoactive substances among students in a Nigerian University: An imperative for intervention programs. *Scientific African*; 16: e01139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2022.e01139>

Adeyemo Florence, O., Beatrice, O., Okpala, P. U. and Oghale, O. (2016). Prevalence of drug abuse amongst university students in Benin City, Nigeria. *Public Health Research*; 6(2): 31–37. <https://doi.org/10.5923/j.phr.20160602.01>

Airede, R. and Asibor, G. (2025). Drug Abuse Patterns among Undergraduates of Select Higher Institutions in Warri Metropolis of Delta State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Sub-Saharan African Research*; 3(1): 579–594. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14564993>

Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)

Alebachew, W., Semahegn, A., Ali, T. and Mekonnen, H. (2019). Prevalence, associated factors and consequences of substance use among health and medical science students of Haramaya University, eastern Ethiopia, 2018: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Psychiatry*; 19(1): 343. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-019-2340-z>

Armoon, B., Griffiths, M. D. and Mohammadi, R. (2023). The global distribution and epidemiology of psychoactive substance use and injection drug use among street-involved children and youth: a meta-analysis. *Substance Use & Misuse*; 58(6): 746–764. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10826084.2023.2181036>

Asagba, R. B., Agberotimi, S. F. and Olaseni, A. O. (2021). Prevalence and psychological correlates of alcohol use among Nigerian university students. *Journal of Substance Use*; 26(6): 608–613. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14659891.2021.1875067>

Attila, F. L., Agyei-Sarpong, K., Asamoah-Gyawu, J., Dadebo, A. A., Eshun, E., Owusu, F. and Barimah, S. J. (2023). Youthful curiosity as a predictor of substance use among students. *Mediterranean Journal of Social & Behavioral Research*; 7(2): 59–64. <https://doi.org/10.30935/mjosbr/1207>

Babalola, E. O., Akinhanmi, A. and Ogunwale, A. (2014). Who guards the guards: drug use pattern among medical students in a nigerian university. *Annals of Medical and Health Sciences Research*; 4(3): 397–403. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2141-9248.133467>

Bandura, A. and Walters, R. H. (1977). *Social learning theory* (Vol. 1). Prentice hall Englewood Cliffs, NJ.

Bio-sya, A., Damien, G. B., Kpatchavi, A. C. and Allabi, A. C. (2022). Prevalence, associated factors and level of dependence of substance use among urban secondary school students, Benin. *Basic & Clinical Pharmacology & Toxicology*; 131(3): 205–213. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bcpt.13764>

Caricati, L. and Ferrari, D. (2021). Association between coping strategies and drug use in a large cohort of students from a northern Italian University. *Acta Bio Medica: Atenei Parmensis*; 92(4): e2021267. <https://doi.org/10.23750/abm.v92i4.11872>

Danpanichkul, P., Duangsonk, K., Diaz, L. A., Chen, V. L., Rangan, P., Sukphutanan, B., Dutta, P., Wanichthanaolan, O., Ramadoss, V. and Sim, B. (2025). The burden of alcohol and substance use disorders in adolescents and young adults. *Drug and Alcohol Dependence*; 266: 112495. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugalcdep.2024.112495>

Dumbili, E. W. (2024). Alcohol industry-sponsored music festivals, alcohol marketing and drinking practices among young Nigerians: Implications for policy. *International Journal of Drug Policy*; 127: 104384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugpo.2024.104384>

Ekekezie, O. O., Daramola, M. K. and Olatona, F. A. (2024). Substance use among undergraduate students at the University of Lagos. *Journal of Community Medicine and Primary Health Care*; 36(3): 47–63. <https://doi.org/10.4314/jcmphc.v36i3.5>

Elemile, M. G., Bello, C. B. and Akinwale, O. D. (2023). Substance abuse among youths in nigeria: implication for community and national health. *Research and Reviews: Journal of Forensic Nursing*; 1(1): 1–15.

Emmanuel, G. O., Akinsolu, F. T., Abodunrin, O. R. and Ezechi, O. C. (2024). Prevalence and patterns of substance use in West Africa: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLOS Global Public Health*; 4(12): e0004019. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgph.0004019>

Espinosa, A., Ruglass, L. M., Conway, F. N., Jackson, K. M. and White, H. R. (2023). Motives, frequency, and consequences of cannabis use among college students. *Journal of Drug Issues*; 53(1): 61–78. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00220426221093608>

Govender, I., Nel, K. and Sibuyi, X. M. (2017). An exploration of alcohol use amongst undergraduate female psychology students at a South African university. *South African Journal of Psychiatry*; 23(1): 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajpsy.2017.23i0.1022>

Htet, H., Saw, Y. M., Saw, T. N., Htun, N. M. M., Lay Mon, K., Cho, S. M., Thike, T., Khine, A. T., Kariya, T. and Yamamoto, E. (2020). Prevalence of alcohol consumption and its risk factors among university students: A cross-sectional study across six universities in Myanmar. *PLoS One*; 15(2): e0229329. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229329>

Jatau, A. I., Sha'aban, A., Gulma, K. A., Shitu, Z., Khalid, G. M., Isa, A., Wada, A. S. and Mustapha, M. (2021). The burden of drug abuse in Nigeria: a scoping review of epidemiological studies and drug laws. *Public Health Reviews*; 42: 1603960. <https://doi.org/10.3389/phrs.2021.1603960>

Johnson, O. E., Akpanekpo, E. I., Okonna, E. M., Adeboye, S. E. and Udoh, A. J. (2017). The prevalence and factors affecting psychoactive substance use among undergraduate students in University of Uyo, Nigeria. *Journal of Community Medicine and Primary Health Care*; 29(2): 11–22.

Kyei-Gyamfi, S., Kyei-Arthur, F., Alhassan, N., Agyekum, M. W., Abrah, P. B. and Kugbey, N. (2024). Prevalence, correlates, and reasons for substance use among adolescents aged 10–17 in Ghana: a cross-sectional convergent parallel mixed-method study. *Substance Abuse Treatment, Prevention, and Policy*; 19(1): 17. [https://doi.org/ 10.1186/s13011-024-00600-2](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13011-024-00600-2)

Lasebikan, V., Lasebikan, T. and Adepoju, S. (2019). Outdoor smoking in Nigeria: prevalence, correlates and predictors. *BMC Public Health*, 19(1): 1313. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-019-7601-8>

Lemma, A., Salelew, E., Demilew, D., Tesfaye, W., Shumet, S. and Kerebih, H. (2021). Alcohol use disorder and associated factors among University of Gondar undergraduate students: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Substance Abuse Treatment*; 129: 108373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsat.2021.108373>

Li, J., Li, X., Shen, Y., Yang, X. and Liu, T. (2025). Global burden attributed to alcohol and drug use among adolescents and young adults, 1990–2019: results from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *BMJ Open*; 15(6): e093412. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2024-093412>

Lorant, V., Nicaise, P., Soto, V. E. and d’Hoore, W. (2013). Alcohol drinking among college students: college responsibility for personal troubles. *BMC Public Health*; 13: 615. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-13-615>

Makinde, O. B., Olatunji, T. T., Okoye, A. M. and Akinola, F. (2022). Substance Use Outcome , Reasons and Preventive Measures : Exploratory Evidence from a Local Government Area in Lagos Nigeria. *Adeleke University Journal of Business and Social Sciences (AUJBSS)*; 1: 103–115. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7891540>

Mekonen, T., Fekadu, W., Mekonnen, T. C. and Workie, S. B. (2017). Substance Use as a Strong Predictor of Poor Academic Achievement among University Students. *Psychiatry Journal*; 2017: 7517450. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/7517450>

Melendro, M., Campos, G., Rodríguez-Bravo, A. E. and Arroyo Resino, D. (2020). Young People’s Autonomy and Psychological Well-Being in the Transition to Adulthood: A Pathway Analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*; 11: 2020. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01946>

Merdassa, A. B. (2024). Traditional masculinity, peer pressure, and sensation seeking as correlates of risky behaviours. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*; 29(1): 2298087. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673843.2023.2298087>

Mokinaro, S., Vincente, J., Benedetti, E., Cerrai, S., Colasante, E., Arpa, S., Chomynová, P., Kraus, L., Monshouwer, K. and Spika, S. (2020). *ESPAD report 2019: Results from European school survey project on alcohol and other drugs*.

Mousavi, M., Tamimi, A., Farsam, M. and Kousha, M. (2024). Substance Abuse and Sleep Quality in University Students. *Addiction and Health*; 16: 35–41. <https://doi.org/10.34172/ahj.2024.1445>

Musyoka, C. M., Mbwayo, A., Donovan, D. and Mathai, M. (2020). Alcohol and substance use among first-year students at the University of Nairobi, Kenya: Prevalence and patterns. *PLOS One*: 15(8): e0238170. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0238170>

Mutiso, V. N., Ndeti, D. M., N. Muia, E., Musyimi, C., Osborn, T. L., Kasike, R., Onsinyo, L., Mbijjiwe, J., Karambu, P. and Sounders, A. (2022). Prevalence and perception of substance abuse and associated economic indicators and mental health disorders in a large cohort of Kenyan students: towards integrated public health approach and clinical management. *BMC Psychiatry*; 22(1): 191. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-022-03817-2>

Necho, M., Belete, A. and Getachew, Y. (2020). The prevalence and factors associated with alcohol use disorder among people living with HIV/AIDS in Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Substance Abuse Treatment, Prevention, and Policy*; 15(1): 63. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13011-020-00301-6>

Ogunkunle, T. O., Gobir, A. A., Makanjuola, A. B. and Ojuawo, A. (2020). Educational status and other socio-demographic correlates of current use of psychoactive substance among Nigerian adolescents. *Nigerian Journal of Paediatrics*; 47(1): 23–29. <https://doi.org/10.4314/njp.v47i1.5>

Okafor, K. C., Bimba, J. S., Adekeye, O. A., Obateru, A. P., Idoko, L. O., Okafor, K. C., Bimba, J. S., Adekeye, O. A., Obateru, A. P. and Idoko, L. O. (2022). The Prevalence and Pattern of Use of Alcohol among Undergraduate Students in Jos Plateau State, Nigeria. *Open Journal of Preventive Medicine*; 12(8): 141–154. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojpm.2022.128011>

Okoro, T. E. and Chikezie, U. E. (2024). Prevalence of alcohol and other psychoactive substance abuse and association with depression among medical students in Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State. *The Pan African Medical Journal*; 47: 90. <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2024.47.90.35997>

Olorunfemi, O., Hamed, O. R. and Oyekanmi, M. (2024). Knowledge and Perceived Effects of Psychoactive Substances among Undergraduate Students of Achievers University, Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria. *APIK Journal of Internal Medicine*; 12(2): 93–98. https://doi.org/10.4103/ajim.ajim_15_23

Oluoha, U. R., Duru, C. B., Okafor, C. C., Diwe, K. C., Iwu, A. C., Aguocha, C. M., Ohale, I. and Nwaigbo, E. (2017). Socio-demographic determinants of psychoactive substance use among students of tertiary institutions in Imo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Addiction Research & Therapy*, 8(5), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2155-6105.1000345>

Onwudebe, P. U. and Elechi, S. O. (2025). Comparative Study of the Prevalence and Determinants of Substance Abuse among Youths in Urban and Rural Communities of Rivers State. *Journal of Health, Applied Sciences and Management*; 9(1): 145–163. <https://doi.org/10.4314/johasam.v9i1.1>

Owoaje, E. T. and Bello, J. (2010). Psychoactive substance use among undergraduate students of the University of Ibadan, Nigeria. *Tropical Journal of Health Sciences*; 17(2). <https://doi.org/10.4314/tjhc.v17i2.61034>

Owolabi, R., Ikonne, C. N. and Ojo, A. I. (2021). Influence of Information Behaviour on Substance Use of Undergraduates in Universities in Ogun State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*; 1–15.

Oyewole, B. K., Animasahun, V. J. and Chapman, H. J. (2018). Tobacco use in Nigerian youth: A systematic review. *PloS One*; 13(5): e0196362. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0196362>

Palin, M. and McConville, K. (2021). Prevalence and perceptions of illicit substance use amongst medical students. *MedEdPublish*; 10: 163. <https://doi.org/10.15694/mep.2021.000163.1>

Scheibe, A., Shelly, S. and Stowe, M. J. (2024). Insights into the value of the market for cocaine, heroin and methamphetamine in South Africa. *Journal of Illicit Economies and Development (JIED)*; 5(3): 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.31389/jied.156>

Schifano, F., Napoletano, F., Chiappini, S., Guirguis, A., Corkery, J. M., Bonaccorso, S., Ricciardi, A., Scherbaum, N. and Vento, A. (2021). New/emerging psychoactive substances and associated psychopathological consequences. *Psychological Medicine*; 51(1): 30–42. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0033291719001727>

Sugden, R., Smith, T. M. F. and Jones, R. (2000). Cochran's Rule for Simple Random Sampling. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B*; 62: 787–793. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9868.00264>

Tsegay, G. (2014). *Psychoactive substances use (khat, alcohol and tobacco) and associated factors among Debre Markos University Students, North-West Ethiopia, 2013*.

Tunagur, M. T. and Kurt Tunagur, E. M. (2026). Substance Use and Suicide Attempts in Adolescents: A Comparative Analysis of Clinical and Psychosocial Risk Factors. *Children*, 13(2), 186. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children13020186>

Ugwu, U. T. (2024). Cannabis swap: gender and tramadol use among Nigerian university students. *Journal of Humanities and Applied Social Sciences*; 6(4): 345–356. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHASS-10-2023-0153>

Umana, J. E., Fawole, O. I. and Adeoye, I. A. (2014). Prevalence and correlates of intimate partner violence towards female students of the University of Ibadan, Nigeria. *BMC Women's Health*; 14: 131. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6874-14-131>

United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. World drug report 2023. (2024). Available at: <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/data-and-analysis/world-drugreport-2023.html>.

Uwaibi, N. E., Omozuwa, E. S., & Agbonrofo-Eboigbe, G. E. (2022). Prevalence, Sociodemographic characteristics and substance abuse among young persons in Edo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management*; 26(2): 361–367.

Wada, Y. H., Khalid, G. M., Shitu, Z. and Ibrahim, U. I. (2021). Prevalence and impacts of psychoactive substance abuse amongst undergraduate university students in Katsina State, Nigeria. *Addiction & Health*; 13(4): 221. <https://doi.org/10.22122/ahj.v13i4.1197>

Willoughby, T., Heffer, T., Good, M. and Magnacca, C. (2021). Is adolescence a time of heightened risk taking? An overview of types of risk-taking behaviors across age groups. *Developmental Review*; 61: 100980. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dr.2021.100980>

WHO Regional Office for Africa (Internet) (2024) (cited 2024 Aug 11). Substance Abuse. Available from: <https://www.afro.who.int/health-topics/substance-abuse>

Xin, Y., Arterberry, B. J. and Davis, A. K. (2025). Multivariate associations between passion, coping motives, and substance use outcomes in college students engaging in simultaneous alcohol and marijuana use. *Journal of Social Work Practice in the Addictions*; 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1533256X.2025.2571512>

